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RE-INTEGRATE Data User Agreement

Preamble

This Data User Agreement articulates the ethical principles and best practices intended to guide users who access and reuse data made openly available by the RE-INTEGRATE project. RE-INTEGRATE, a Horizon Europe-funded project, is dedicated to fostering climate-compatible energy strategies through collaboration between the African Union and the European Union. We are committed to promoting open and accessible research data, while upholding the principles of responsible and ethical data use.

Purpose of this Agreement

This Data User Agreement is not a legally binding contract. Instead, it serves as a voluntary framework based on ethical principles and community norms for responsible data sharing and reuse. Its core purposes are to:

- Promote the responsible and ethical reuse of RE-INTEGRATE data.
- Encourage proper attribution and citation of RE-INTEGRATE data, acknowledging the work of data creators.
- Ensure users are aware of the intended uses, limitations, and context of the data.
- Foster a culture of collaboration, transparency, and mutual respect within the energy research and policy community.

Data Usage Terms

By accessing and using data made available by RE-INTEGRATE, you are indicating your understanding of and agreement to adhere to the following terms and conditions:

1. **Permitted Use:** You are encouraged to reuse RE-INTEGRATE data for non-commercial research, educational, and policy analysis purposes. This includes, but is not limited to:
 - Scientific research and analysis
 - Educational activities and curriculum development
 - Informing policy development and strategic energy planning
 - Developing new models and tools
 - Creating visualizations and presentations

2. **Attribution and Citation:** Proper attribution is essential for acknowledging the work of data creators and ensuring the traceability of research outputs. When using RE-INTEGRATE data, you agree to:
 - Clearly cite the dataset in any publications, reports, presentations, or other outputs that utilize RE-INTEGRATE data.
 - Include the Zenodo DOI (Digital Object Identifier) of the dataset in your citation.
 - Acknowledge the RE-INTEGRATE project and the European Union's Horizon Europe funding (Grant Agreement No. 101118217) in your acknowledgements section.
 - *(Recommended Citation Format Example):* RE-INTEGRATE Project. (2024). *Proficiency Badges for Energy and Resource System Modelling (Version v2)*. Zenodo. **doi:10.5281/zenodo.14231392**
3. **Data Integrity and Responsible Modification:** While you are permitted to adapt and modify RE-INTEGRATE data for your own research purposes, you agree to:
 - Clearly acknowledge any modifications or adaptations made to the original data in your documentation and outputs.
 - Utilize the data responsibly and ethically, ensuring that it is not misrepresented, misinterpreted, or employed in any way that could compromise its integrity or lead to misleading conclusions.
4. **No Warranty and Disclaimer:** RE-INTEGRATE data is provided "as is," for research and educational purposes, without any warranty, express or implied. This includes, but is not limited to, any warranties regarding data accuracy, completeness, reliability, or fitness for a particular purpose. RE-INTEGRATE and its partners shall not be held liable for any direct or indirect damages, losses, or consequences resulting from the use or misuse of the data.
5. **Ethical Considerations:** You agree to use RE-INTEGRATE data in an ethical and responsible manner, respecting data privacy, confidentiality, and intellectual property rights. You agree not to use the data for any malicious, harmful, or discriminatory purposes.

Contact Information

For any inquiries regarding the RE-INTEGRATE Data User Agreement or RE-INTEGRATE data, please contact the RE-INTEGRATE Data Manager:

- **Data Manager:** Dr. Xiufeng Liu
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- **Project Website:** <https://re-integrate-au.eu/>

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